

ORIGINAL INVESTIGATION

Comparison of Flexural Strength of Conventional Nanohybrid Composite Resins vs. 3D-Printed Resins for Definitive Restorations. *In Vitro Study*

Comparación de la resistencia a la flexión de resinas compuestas nanohíbridas convencionales vs. resinas impresas en 3D para restauraciones definitivas. Estudio in vitro

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To compare the flexural strength of conventional nanohybrid composite resin and 3D-printed resin used as definitive materials before and after thermocycling. Methodology: Type of research - experimental, In vitro, comparative. A total of 90 specimens were fabricated, divided into two groups of 45 samples each: conventional nanohybrid composite resin and 3D-printed resin. The study established the formation of four groups: Group A-1: Conventional nanohybrid composite resin without thermocycling (n=22), Group A-2: Conventional nanohybrid composite resin + 5000 thermocycling cycles (n=23), Group B-1: 3D-printed resin without thermocycling (n=22), and Group B-2: 3D-printed resin + 5000 thermocycling cycles (n=23). The specimens were fabricated following ISO 4049 standards (bars of 25x2x2mm). The conventional resins were prepared on a stainless steel matrix for subsequent polymerization, while the 3D-printed resins were designed using software. The samples underwent polishing, thermocycling, and calibration. The four groups were subjected to loads using a universal testing machine (Universidad de las Fuerzas Armadas, Materials Mechanics Laboratory) to measure flexural strength and compare the results. The results were analyzed using normality and homogeneity tests, specifically the Shapiro-Wilk test, which determined that the values were not normally distributed. Consequently, the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was applied to compare the study variables. Results: Among the four groups subjected to load testing using the universal testing machine, the conventional nanohybrid composite resins without thermocycling showed an average flexural strength of 151.22±6.89 MPa, followed by thermocycled conventional nanohybrid composite resins with 103.56±7.13 MPa, 3D-printed resins

without thermocycling with 96.85 ± 6.52 MPa, and finally, thermocycled 3D-printed resins with 86.77 ± 2.60 MPa. Conclusions: The conventional nanohybrid composite resin that was not subjected to thermocycling exhibited the highest flexural strength, with an average of 151.22 MPa, compared to the other groups, whose values were significantly lower. However, the thermocycled conventional nanohybrid composite resin and the non-thermocycled 3D-printed resin did not present statistically significant differences.

Keywords: Flexural strength. Nanohybrid resins. 3D-printed resin. Thermocycling. Definitive material

INTRODUCTION

Dental resins have made a significant contribution to dentistry because of their excellent optical, physical, and mechanical properties. They have been used as restorative materials because they mimic the lost dental structure and are therefore constantly subjected to occlusal loads. For this reason, they must possess high strength and durability to ensure satisfactory performance. These materials should be evaluated under conditions similar to those of the oral cavity by using thermocycling in *in vitro* studies. This method allows for the assessment of whether there is a significant difference between conventional and 3D printed resins, providing substantial insights into their mechanical properties.

Digitally assisted dentistry has led to the introduction of innovative materials that now allow clinicians to opt for 3D-printed resins, which can be used as provisional or definitive materials in various treatments. This advancement significantly reduces fabrication time compared with conventional methods and streamlines clinical protocols across all dental specialties [1]. However, the rise of digitally assisted dentistry has brought with it a wide array of new materials for each type of dental treatment. Due to the vast number of available compounds and products on the market, conducting thorough research on each material's properties is almost impossible [2].

While there is extensive information available on the mechanical properties of conventional nanohybrid composite resins, data on 3D printed resins remains limited. Although manufacturers provide some studies, they are often insufficient to ensure clinical success. Flexural strength is one of the most relevant mechanical properties, as polymerizable resins in the oral cavity are subject to intraoral forces and humid

environments. Therefore, these materials must be reliable, durable, and suitable for use in the oral cavity [3,4]. This difference between digitally assisted and conventional dentistry leads to the following research question: Is there a difference in flexural strength between conventional nanohybrid composite resin and 3D-printed resin, and what is the effect of thermocycling on these materials?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Type of Study

This is an experimental, *in vitro*, and comparative study, the population consisted of conventional nanohybrid composite resins and 3D-printed resins used for definitive restorations. The following inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied to select and standardize the specimens for the study (see Table 1).

A total of 90 bar-shaped samples were fabricated according to ISO 4049 standards, with dimensions of 25 mm in length, 2 mm in width, and 2 mm in thickness. The samples were distributed into four groups: Group A-1 consisted of 22 samples of conventional nanohybrid composite resin without thermocycling; Group A-2 included 23 samples of conventional nanohybrid composite resin subjected to 000 thermocycling cycles; Group B-1 comprised 22 samples of 3D-printed resin without thermocycling; and Group B-2 included 23 samples of 3D-printed resin subjected to 5000 thermocycling cycles.

All samples were numbered and standardized to ensure reproducibility. Flexural strength was evaluated using a three-point bending test on a properly calibrated universal testing machine.

Method

A stainless steel mold was fabricated using laser cutting, in accordance with ISO 4049 standards, with the required dimensions (25 mm length, 2 mm width, 2 mm thickness). To facilitate the removal of resin specimens, vertical and horizontal cuts were made in the steel, allowing for easier extraction after curing, the plate is divided into two parts, but they can be joined together when filling the space in the form of a bar with the resin.

Figure 1. Fabrication of a stainless steel mold

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

The following materials were necessary for the preparation of the 45 specimens of conventional nanohybrid composite resin:

- a) Stainless steel mold
- b) Tetric N-Ceram A2 nanohybrid resin
- c) Gutta-percha
- d) Brush
- e) Glycerin
- f) VALO light-curing lamp
- g) Digital caliper
- h) Sandpapers 1000, 1500, and 2000
- i) 4 glass slides
- j) 2 strips of celluloid

Figure 2. Materials for the preparation of resin bars.

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

Measurement of the stainless steel mold with the digital caliper, ensuring that it meets ISO 4049 standards: 25 mm in length, 2 mm in width, and 2 mm in thickness.

Figure 3. Calibration of the stainless steel mold.

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

The glass slide had the following dimensions: 1.07 mm in thickness, 25.27 mm in width, and 76 mm in length. It is important that the glass slide used to apply pressure to the resin when it is compacted completely has a thickness of 1 mm, as this is the ideal distance for initiating photopolymerization.

Figure 4. Dimensions of the glass slide.

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

On one of the glass slides, which will function as the base, a strip of celluloid will be placed. Then, the stainless steel mold will be placed on top. Once this is done, a brush will be dipped in glycerin and removed, applying pressure to the edges of the glycerin bottle to remove any excess. The mold will then be lubricated inside the stainless steel mold to create a barrier between the resin and the metal.

Figure 5. Isolation of the stainless steel mold with glycerin.

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

Figure 6. Incremental layers of resin inside the stainless steel mold.

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

Once the mold is isolated, the composite resin (Tetric N Ceram) will be incorporated and compacted incrementally using a gutta-percha point inside the bar-shaped space within the metal mold.

Once the space in the mold is filled with resin, a strip of celluloid will be placed on top, followed by another glass slide to apply pressure. The purpose of this action is to remove any excess resin.

Figure 7. Compaction and removal of excess resin.

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

Afterward, with the VALO light-curing lamp at an angle of 180° , the head, which has a diameter of 9.75 mm, will be placed against the glass slide and activated for 20 seconds on the bottom part. Once this cycle is completed, the lamp will be positioned in the same way

on the middle part of the mold for 20 seconds. Finally, it will be placed on the top part of the mold for 20 seconds.

The mold will then be flipped to the reverse side and photopolymerized in the same manner as the front side until the entire sample is polymerized.

Figure 8. Photocuring with a state-of-the-art light-curing lamp.

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

Once the entire resin is polymerized, the stainless steel mold will be segmented into two parts to obtain the bar-shaped specimen. This process for preparing the resin bars with the indicated dimensions will be repeated until 45 specimens are obtained.

Figure 9. Extraction of the resin specimen

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

Once the 45 required specimens are prepared, excess resin will be removed due to irregularities to ensure they meet the inclusion criteria. Sandpapers with numbers from lowest to highest, 1000, 1500, and 2000, will be used.

After completely removing the irregularities from the 45 specimens, all the bars will be measured with the digital caliper to ensure they meet the criteria according to ISO 4049 standards: 25 mm in length, 2 mm in width, and 2 mm in thickness. All conventional

nanohybrid composite resin specimens that meet the inclusion criteria will be coded.

Figure 10. Calibrated and standardized conventional nanohybrid composite resin specimens, 45 samples

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

For the fabrication of the 45 resin specimens in bar shape according to ISO 4049 standards, a 3D design software, MESHMIXER, will be used to create STL files, which will then be imported into 3D printing software to organize the printing session.

Figure 11. 3D bar design in MESHMIXER

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

Once the bars were designed with the indicated dimensions of 25 mm in length, 2 mm in width, and 2 mm in thickness in the program, they were configured and standardized with a resolution of 50 μ m on the SprintRay Pro S printer to print 45 samples using Crown resin, which is intended for definitive indirect restorations such as single-unit crowns, inlays, onlays, and veneers.

Once the machine has finished printing the 45 specimens, they must be washed in an ultrasonic bath with 90% isopropyl alcohol, following the manufacturer's instructions, for 10 minutes to disinfect any resin impurities.

Once the cleaning of the specimens is completed, they will be polymerized through a post curing chamber for the time indicated by the manufacturer, approximately between 3 and 5 minutes, at a power of 385 nm, using

LED light. After the photopolymerization process is completed, the specimens will be polished to eliminate any irregularities.

Once the specimens were printed and their entire protocol completed for delivery, the 45 bars were measured with a digital caliper to ensure they met the criteria according to ISO 4049 standards: 25 mm in length, 2 mm in width, and 2 mm in thickness. All 3D-printed resin specimens that met the inclusion criteria will be coded.

For the preservation of the 90 specimens until they are subjected to the flexural strength tests, they will be stored in amber-colored jars containing 100 ml of distilled water. These jars will be labeled according to the corresponding groups for the study (Group A-1, A-2, and Group B-1, B-2).

After the 90 specimens have been selected and preserved according to the inclusion criteria, 23 specimens of conventional nanohybrid composite resin (blue) and 23 specimens of 3D-printed resin (red) will be randomly designated and identified to undergo the aging process with 5000 cycles, while the remaining specimens, 22 of conventional nanohybrid composite resin and 22 of 3D-printed resin, will be preserved in jars with distilled water.

The specimens that will undergo aging will be placed in the thermocycler until reaching 5000 cycles, which is equivalent to 1 year in the oral cavity. The cycle number was set to immerse the specimens in water at two different temperatures ($5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.5$ and $55^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.5$) for 16 seconds at each temperature. Once the 5000 cycles are completed, the specimens will be returned to the jars with distilled water for transport to the laboratory, where the flexural strength tests will be conducted.

Flexural strength tests

A total of 90 specimens were subjected to flexural strength testing using the MTS T/5002 universal testing machine, located in the Materials Mechanics Laboratory of the Universidad de las Fuerzas Armadas ESPE. The laboratory staff conducted and supervised the entire process, ensuring optimal testing conditions. The results were systematically

recorded on a data collection sheet, with clear identification of each group: A-1, A-2, B-1, and B-2. The following equation was used to calculate the flexural strength in megapascals (MPa), substituting the corresponding values for each specimen: (MPa):

$$\sigma = \frac{3Fl}{2bh^2}$$

Where:

F= the maximum load, in newtons, applied to the specimen.

l= the distance, in millimeters, between the supports, with a precision of 0.01 mm.

b= the width, in millimeters, at the center of the specimen, measured immediately before the test.

h= the height, in millimeters, at the center of the specimen, measured immediately before the test.

A load was applied at the center of the diameter to the nanohybrid and 3D-printed resin specimens, until the bending point, at a speed of 1 mm/min.

Statistics

With the aim of comparing the flexural strength of

conventional nanohybrid composite resins and 3D-printed resins, an experimental, In Vitro, comparative study was conducted on 45 conventional nanohybrid resin samples and 45 3D-printed resins, both without thermocycling and with 5000 cycles in the thermocycler. The data obtained were analyzed using normality and homogeneity tests, specifically the Shapiro-Wilk test, to determine if the data followed a normal distribution. The results indicated that the data were not normally distributed, so the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was applied to compare the variables under study.

The four resin groups were subjected to loads using the universal testing machine, where it was observed that the non-thermocycled conventional nanohybrid resins showed a mean of 151.22±6.89 MPa, followed by the thermocycled conventional nanohybrid resins with 103.56±7.13 MPa, the non-thermocycled 3D-printed resins with 96.85±6.52 MPa, and finally the thermocycled 3D-printed resins with 86.77±2.60 MPa.

Table 1. Average Flexural Strength (MPa) of Nanohybrid Resins and 3D Printed Resins with and without Thermocycling.

Resinas	Media	D.E	Mínimo	Máximo
R. nanohíbrida ST	151,22	6,89	142,50	165,00
R. impresa 3D ST	96,85	6,52	90,00	108,80
R. nanohíbrida T	103,56	7,13	93,80	116,30
R. impresa 3D T	86,77	2,60	82,50	90,00

Resina IT= Resina impresa termociclada, Resina I ST= Resina impresa sin termociclado,

Resina NT= Resina Nanohíbrida termociclada, Resina N ST= Resina Nanohíbrida sin termociclado.

Fuente: Elaboracion propia

RESULTS

When performing pairwise comparisons of resins, it was observed that most comparisons showed p-values of 0.000, indicating a statistically significant difference between the means of the resin groups. This suggests that different types of resins have distinct properties or performances. However, when comparing the 3D printed resin without thermocycling and the nanohybrid resin with thermocycling, a p-value ≥ 0.05 was observed, suggesting that these two groups behave similarly.

DISCUSSION

In recent years, restorative dentistry has experienced exponential growth in the use of digital technologies, leading to the need for scientific research in this area. 3D printing technology, in particular, has overcome the limitations of traditional manufacturing systems in dentistry, thanks to the development of new materials and the continuous improvement of 3D printers (16). This technology is used to manufacture a wide range of biomaterials for dental treatments, surgeries, and medical devices. In the field of dentistry, 3D printing is mainly employed to create dental implants, orthodontic models, metal restorations, surgical guides for implants, and temporary crowns (16,17,18,26). Due to its numerous advantages, it has been proposed for use in permanent fixed restorations (18).

In dentistry, materials used in the oral cavity are exposed to various stresses, such as masticatory forces and parafunctional habits. Therefore, flexural strength is a fundamental property of these materials, as it determines their ability to absorb and withstand loads and to prevent crack propagation (20,21). Adequate flexural strength allows the restoration to evenly distribute forces across its structure, contributing to its durability and long-term clinical success. Besides flexural strength, other mechanical properties critical to the success of restorations include microhardness and fatigue resistance. These properties ensure that the material can withstand masticatory forces without fracturing or displacing (34).

The nanohybrid resin (Tetric N-Ceram) exhibits superior flexural strength compared to 3D printed resins, with values that meet and exceed the minimum threshold set by the ISO 4049 standard. These findings align with previous studies that reported that nanohybrid resins, like Tetric N-Ceram, have a more homogeneous structure and lower porosity, contributing to their better mechanical performance.

The scarcity of studies on the physicomechanical properties of 3D printed resins with ceramic fillers for definitive restorations is a significant issue. This lack of

research can create uncertainty regarding the long-term durability and performance of these restorations. Therefore, it is essential to compare the flexural strength of conventional nanohybrid composite resins with 3D printed resins with ceramic fillers (Crown) through an experimental in vitro study.

The results showed that the flexural stress in 3D printed resins was lower compared to nanohybrid resins, with average values of 96.85 MPa for 3D resins without thermocycling and 86.76 MPa after thermocycling. The mechanical properties of 3D resins for flexural strength were below the thresholds specified by the ISO 4049 standard (38), which sets a minimum of 100 MPa. These results are consistent with other studies (27), which reported similar values. However, they differ from the results obtained by De Angelis et al., in 2024 (28), who reported significantly higher flexural strength values (between 135.0 and 101.3 MPa). Another study (38) found flexural strength values ranging from 123.4 ± 8.7 MPa, 109.9 ± 15.8 for non-aged groups, and 97.5 ± 15.2 MPa, and 94.2 ± 11.7 MPa for thermocycled groups. These discrepancies could be attributed to differences in the methodologies used to measure flexural strength and the characteristics of the printed samples, possibly a resin with higher filler content or a different formulation.

In contrast to our findings, Sahin Z et al. in 2023 (35) reported flexural strength values of 218.90 MPa for resins manufactured by subtraction and 87.83 MPa for resins made additively. This discrepancy could be due to methodological differences, as the reported study was conducted according to the ISO 6872:2015 standard using a three-point bending test. It is important to note that the sample geometry for this test differs between restorative composite resins and ceramics (36,37).

Borella et al. (35) in 2023 investigated the mechanical properties of four 3D resins, varying the layer thickness (50 and 100 μm) and following the ISO 4049:2020 standard. After an initial curing of 30 minutes, they reported a flexural strength of 124 ± 77 MPa for the 50 μm thickness and 115 ± 12.8 MPa for the 100 μm

thickness. However, they observed that flexural strength significantly increased when the post-polymerization time was extended to over 60 minutes. These differences may be attributed to the influence of curing time, which was done following the manufacturer's recommendations of 3 to 5 minutes with a power of 385 nm.

Liebermann et al. (32) conducted a three-point bending test on 3D resin samples perpendicular to the platform and rotated 45 degrees on the X and Y axes, without following the ISO 4049:2020 standard, yielding average flexural strength values of 119 MPa for the perpendicular samples and 143 MPa for those rotated 45 degrees. These findings highlight the importance of continuing to investigate and optimize the properties of 3D printed resins and their variables, which can produce different statistical values when considering everything from design to printing for clinical use in dentistry.

3D printed resins exhibit differences in their physicomechanical properties compared to conventional nanohybrid resins ($p=0.000$). The differences in the results across groups may be attributed to variations in the chemical compositions and viscosities of the materials. Additionally, reinforcing these resins with additives appears to be a promising strategy to improve their strength and performance. Various studies (29,30,31) suggest that incorporating certain additives, such as filler nanoparticles or fibers, can significantly increase the flexural strength of 3D resins, bringing them closer to the properties of nanohybrid resins. However, it is crucial to follow appropriate guidelines when adding additives to ensure they do not negatively affect the color, flow, light penetration depth, or increase post-curing time and temperature. Furthermore, the layer thickness during printing plays a critical role in the degree of resin polymerization and, therefore, its final properties (33). Continuous research and development of new techniques and materials are essential to optimizing the properties of 3D printed resins and expanding their use in modern dentistry.

The aging of dental materials aims to simulate the conditions of humidity and temperature they experience in the oral cavity. In this study, the thermocycled resin group underwent 5000 cycles, simulating one year in the oral cavity, with the samples submerged in water at two different temperatures ($5^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.5$ and $55^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.5$). After this thermocycling process, our investigation observed a decrease in flexural strength values compared to the non-thermocycled samples ($p=0.000$), data similar to those found in the study by Di Fiore et al. (38) in 2024, which aimed to evaluate and compare the mechanical properties of two commercially available 3D printed resins for definitive restorations after artificial aging. The decrease in values in the aged groups is likely due to direct contact with water, which can increase liquid sorption in the samples, negatively affecting their mechanical properties (35,36). Liquid sorption can weaken the material's matrix and/or interfere with intermolecular forces, reducing flexural strength.

The null hypotheses proposed in this research project are rejected, as the results presented by the four resin groups tested were all statistically different in the flexural strength tests.

A recent systematic review conducted in 2025 (39) concluded that 3D printed resins exhibit lower flexural strength, fatigue behavior, and microhardness compared to other resins used for both temporary and permanent restorations. Additionally, this review highlights that the type of 3D printing technology used, the type of printer, polymerization time, and post-processing procedures significantly influence these mechanical properties of 3D printed resins. This suggests that while conventional resins are still the most resistant option, 3D printing technologies present a promising alternative in restorative dentistry, particularly in applications where speed and precision in fit are determining factors.

CONCLUSIONS

The flexural strength of the nanohybrid composite resins without thermocycling (Group A-1) was an average of 151.22 ± 6.89 MPa, while the 3D printed resins without thermocycling (Group B-2) had an

average of 96.85 ± 6.52 MPa, showing significantly higher resistance in the conventional nanohybrid composite resins. The flexural strength of the thermocycled nanohybrid composite resins (Group A-2) was 103.56 ± 7.13 MPa, while the thermocycled 3D printed resins (Group B-2) had values of 86.77 ± 2.60 MPa, showing significantly lower resistance in the 3D printed resins.

Pairwise comparisons of resins showed statistically significant differences between group means. These results demonstrate that different resin groups exhibit statistically different properties or performances. Group A-1 had the highest flexural strength with an average of 151.22 ± 6.89 MPa, followed by Group A-2 with 103.56 ± 7.13 MPa, then Group B-1 with 96.85 ± 6.52 MPa, and lastly Group B-2 with values lower than the rest, showing 86.77 ± 2.60 MPa. However, the comparison between the conventional nanohybrid composite resin with thermocycling and the 3D printed resin without thermocycling showed a p -value ≥ 0.05 , suggesting a similar behavior between these two groups.

Artificial aging or thermocycling was shown to be relevant, as it can degrade the mechanical properties of resins, but these can only be evaluated through specific tests that provide quantitative data, as it is impossible to determine material performance deterioration solely by observation.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.